

A mini-review on functional multilayered materials

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Abstract

Multilayered materials are ubiquitous in nature offering a wide range of relevant functionalities, going from mechanical performance to complex biosynthesis processes. In materials engineering, biomimicry or bio-inspiration approaches have been effective strategies to develop complex multifunctional materials. The rational combination of the properties of different materials in multilayer systems have been capitalized in science and engineering for several practical applications. In this document, we review literature that present multilayered materials for different applications: mechanically enhanced materials, tissue-engineering, energy and sensing. The interest in these multifunctional materials comes not only from their properties but also from the great possibilities of extrapolating their usage in seemingly unrelated areas with innovative techniques.

Keywords: multilayer, bioinspired, multifunctional materials

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1. Introduction

Structured materials demand has increased in high-performance applications in engineering and medical areas throughout the years. In order to fulfill these demands, a great interest in nature-inspired architecture has risen in the last decade (Liu et al. [1] Bandyopadhyay et al. [2] Xu et al. [3]). The imitation of natural patterns, such as multilayered structures, is present in newly designed technologies (Mukhopadhyay et al. [4] Yang et al. [5] Jiang et al. [6] Lee et al. [7]). Ductility, conductivity, biocompatibility, and porosity are some of the characteristics a multilayered architecture can attribute to a material (Marino et al. [8], Zhu et al. [9], Qiu et al. [10], Yang et al. [5]).

Figure 1: Graphical representation of this work's focus.

Figure 1 showcases applications in which natural multilayers have found a niche. The geometry of the multilayers in this work focus can be described as one where the thickness in the growth direction is small compared to their dimensions in the plane of the layers, exemplified in **figure 1**. Even though the architecture of the multiple layers revised in this work is very similar, the properties attributed to each structural arrangement are very different, depending on methodologies, reinforcements, and chemical interactions between layers. Mechanical, electrical, controlled drug delivery, sensing, and tissue engineering multilayered constructs will be revised in the present work.

2. Properties of multi-layer systems

Having multiple properties simultaneously in a material is a trend. Through selected examples from the literature, the architecture repercussions in the behavior and application of the multilayer systems will be analyzed, with special emphasis on mechanical, electrical, drug delivery, sensing, and tissue engineering.

2.1. Mechanical

Preventing fractures and strengthening of materials in industrial construction applications are properties of special interest nowadays. Multilayers of one or more materials have been proven useful in improving the young modulus, mode II interlaminar fracture, poisson ratio, shear strength, and ductility (Shin et al. [11], Kim and Lee [12], [13], Malas et al. [14]). Natural shells, bones, and wood are some bioinspiration for multilayer materials that have multiscale hierarchical structures. Lamination, protrusions, and network structures in different scales inside these naturally multilayered materials work together to give the strengthening and toughening effects. Current literature about these topics are presented in **figure 2**. Enhanced mechanical properties can be obtained when nanosized particles are incorporated into a matrix; these materials are called nanocomposites (Mukhopadhyay et al. [4], Kim and Lee [12]). Various engineering industries, like aerospace and automobile industry, have turned their attention to polymer nanocomposites to strengthen materials widely used by them, specially epoxy resins (Schilde et al. [15], Idrees et al. [16]).

Epoxy resins are the most common thermosetting polymers. These resins are prepared from a liquid precursor that after undergoing heating, irreversibly transforms to a solid material. CNTs incorporation into epoxy laminates were used by Shin et al. [11] to produce a nanocomposite, carbon fiber-reinforced plastic (CFRP), with enhanced mechanical properties (**figure 2A**). Carbon nanotubes (CNTs), nearly one-dimensional nanoparticles, are well known for their capability for enhancing mechanical properties Aqel et al. [17]. The methodology reported by the authors, shown in **figure 2 Ai**, was based on two techniques: three-roll milling to obtain thin layers of CNTs/epoxy resin, and ultrasonication to obtain the pure epoxy film layer. Once the two thin layers of materials were produced, B-staging was used to

Figure 2: Mechanical properties of multilayer laminate systems. **A**) CFRP) laminates reinforced with CNTs: **i**) Three-roll milling technique, **ii**) Resulted architecture, **iii**) Mode II fracture toughness with respect of the CNTs percentage (%wt) [17]. **B**) Woven glass fiber reinforced composites: **i**) Additive manufacturing methodology, **ii**) Experimental results, **iii**) Flexural stress–strain curves [16]. **C**) MMCs composites: **i**) Hot rolling technique, **ii**) Ni and Cu multilayers; **iii**) Tensile stress-strain curves [24]. **D**) Multilayer steel. **i**) Layers assembly through rolling and annealing treatment, **ii**) EPMA mapping for the tensile fracture characteristics analysis, **iii**) Tensile curves of raw and cold-rolled (blue line) multilayer steels (cold-rolled possesses the highest tensile strength and yield strength, reaching 1035 MPa and 879 MPa respectively) [28].

fix the CNTS/Epoxy and Epoxy layers together. B-staging technique utilizes heat or UV light to remove the majority of solvent from an adhesive, to prevent complete polymerization of the resin system, thereby, allowing the layers to be “staged” one next to each other Iakoubovskii [18]. The results of the resulting multilayer material were more optimal at the 3 wt% CNT/epoxy film-interleaving concentration, as shown in **figure 2 Aii**, enhancing their mode II fracture toughness by 126.7%. Agglomeration of CNTs in higher concentrations (CNT loading at 9 wt%) decreased toughness, aligning with the conclusions of reported literature (Feng et al. [19], Schilde et al. [15], Ma et al. [20]). Other works suggest the amino-functionalization of CNTs for a better dispersion, and interfacial interaction for CNT/epoxy composites (Ma et al. [20]).

Woven glass fibers are another type of material widely used in industry that can be mechanically improved by multilayer techniques. Traditional ways to manufacture glass fiber composites, like Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding (VARTM), are efficient but usually they have poor out-of-plane mechanical properties (Barbosa et al. [21]). Out-of plane mechanical properties of materials are dependent on the perpendicular forces applied to their surfaces. Internally aligned resins and glass fiber composites have excellent in-plane properties, but they are insignificant if the out-of-plane properties are not improved (Liu et al. [22]).

Multilayers can improve them solely because of their alignment and thickness control in them. Idrees et al. [16] used the 3D vat polymerization technique, to obtain woven glass fiber reinforced multilayered composites (see **figure 2Bi**). The architecture obtained by the Resin Rich Layers (RRL) of Idrees et al. [16] is shown in **figure 2Bii**. This additive manufacturing technique was proven to help in spacing, thickness, and location precision of the 16 layers printed, crucial aspects when fabricating multilayer materials (Idrees et al. [16], Medellin et al. [23], Malas et al. [14]). Mode II interlaminar fracture toughness was improved by 300%. This important enhancement, from 0.52 to 2.02 KJ/m² when adding 100 μ m RRL, could be achieved because of the reduction of the stress concentration at the resin-fiber interface that multilayers cause, which creates larger plastic yield zones.

Composites with metal matrices and alloys can also be benefited by a multilayered architecture, often using rolling techniques (see **figures 2 Ci**,

and 2 Di). Alloys and metal matrix composites (MMCs) are greatly used in the aerospace and transportation industry overall (Wang et al. [24]). Reports show that the mechanical properties of multilayered MMCs can be enhanced by using nanoparticles as reinforcements due to the nanoscale arrangement they provide. In **figure 2 Ci**, a hot rolling technique is exemplified for the obtention of Cu/Graphene/Ni multilayer composites, showing a physical way to obtain this architecture ([13]). The Ni and Cu layers are appreciated in **figure 2 Cii**. The tensile stress-strain curves in **figure 2 Ciii** are clear evidence of the internal anatomic dynamic for the storage of the material's dislocations, which are defects in the internal structure of the material. When increasing the strain rate, the motion suppression of the dislocation of the composite is attributed to the flow stress, which parallelly decreases the recovery of the dislocations, affecting the ductility capacity (Estrin and Mecking [25]). Even though this behavior was observed, the ductility was not affected as much as in MMCs with no graphene reinforcement, attributing the ductility to this nanoparticle, agreeing with literature (Mukhopadhyay and Adhikari [26], Li [27]).

Alloys, like steel, can be strengthened and toughened by intercalating layers as well. Zhang et al. [28] shows a cold rolling and annealing technique (**figure 2 Di**) to obtain a 60-layers-multiscale hierarchical structure, which provides an advantage in alloy element diffusion properties. An Electron probe micro-analyzer (EPMA) area analysis of this multilayered steel architecture is shown in **figure 2 Dii**, where no evident cracks were found due to the multilayered arrangement. The tensile curve of the intercalated 30 layers of A283-C carbon steel layers and 30 layers of SUS304 austenite stainless steel is shown in **figure 2 Diii**, demonstrating that the cold temperature in the rolling technique leads to the steel with more ductility.

Layers intercalation, thus, can improve mechanical properties of materials like mode II interlaminar fracture, out-of-plane mechanics, shear strength, and ductility. Physical methodologies coupled with chemical processes can synergize to give the mechanical robustness necessary for a material. Nanoparticles reinforcements, such as GO and CNTs, can help make mechanically robust composite materials due to the synergy achieved with the matrix's properties. The number of layers, preventing agglomeration, and the thickness of each layer play an important role in resilient multilayer materials.

2.2. Electrical

Layer intercalation for the enhancement of electronic properties has been an approach used for many years (Jiang et al. [29], Wang et al. [30], Chávez-Madero et al. [31]). Currently, new processes for achieving multilayer architecture using additive manufacturing, self assembling techniques or hydrothermal techniques have awakened interest for bettering the ionic transfer in electronics, together with their wearable potential. The incorporation of nanomaterials in these new processes is common. (Mukhopadhyay et al. [4], Kim and Lee [12], Mukhopadhyay [32], Shipway et al. [33]). With the correct concentration and distribution, nanomaterials can enhance wearables, supercapacitors, and electrodes's conductive capacity (Mukhopadhyay [32], Biswas and Drzal [34], Park et al. [35]). Also, insulator layers, such like the ones found in electric eels, are necessary in between conductive materials in some architectures. In **figure 3**, some newly developed methods are shown.

The development of multilayered systems to achieve various tunable desired properties simultaneously has been studied in the last decade (Mukhopadhyay [32], Shipway et al. [33]). Several ways to assemble these monolayers have been reported. Controlled swelling (see **figure 3Ai**) was a technique used by Zhu et al. [36] to obtain multilayer graphene hydrogels. Two-dimensional materials, such as graphene, are attractive for conductivity due to its large Van der Waals attraction between their basal plane with a conjugated polymer in a layered composite structure, leading to excellent electrical properties (Biswas and Drzal [34], Falkovsky and Varlamov [37], Liu et al. [38]) The incorporation of graphene required a pretreatment of graphene oxide (GO) nanosheets. This process is important, because it reduces the pi-pi stacking of the GO nanosheets with each other, a requirement to increase their electronic transport (Niu et al. [39], Xu et al. [40]). The resulting graphene hydrogel films follow a multilayer, porous, and highly orientated architecture, shown in **figure 3Aii**. The films were assembled in a Zinc-ion hybrid supercapacitor to test its capacitance, exhibiting values up to 99.3 mAh g⁻¹ of capacitance, making it attractive for electronic applications (Zhu et al. [36]). Another innovative way to assemble porous nanosheets is layer-by-layer assembly (Wang et al. [41], Wang et al. [42], Taheri et al. [43]). A similar porous electrode was produced utilizing layer-by-layer coupled with filtration by Wu et al. [44] (see **figure 3Bi**). A cross-sectional SEM image (see **figure 3Bii**) shows the layers within the construct. which lead to 45.4 mAh cm⁻² of areal capacity, a number that surpasses by one order of mag-

Figure 3: Electrical properties of multilayer systems. **A)** Supercapacitors by controlled-swelling of GO: **i** Methodology, **ii** Graphene hydrogel architecture, **iii** Cyclic voltammetry curves [36]. **B)** Thick porous nanosheets electrode: **i** Layer-by-layer assembly, **ii** SEM 50 micrometer and 100 nm resolution images, **iii** Capacity analysis curves [44]. **C)** Conductive cellulose nanofiber: **i** Spontaneous self-assembly methodology, **ii** Multilayered architecture, **iii** Compact density analysis [45]. **D)** MXene/graphene supercapacitors: **i** Wet-spinning technique, **ii** SEM 10 micrometers and 500 nm, **iii** Cyclic voltammetry curves [56].

nitude the areal capacity of commercial cathodes Wu et al. [44].

Biswas and Drzal [34] and [45] used self-assembly techniques to produce a multilayered nano and microarchitecture in conductive polymers. Biswas and Drzal [34]'s methodology consisted on aligning monolayers of graphene nanosheets for their later interspersing within a fibrous network of a conductive polymer, polypyrrole, giving a highly ionic property to the material. Cellulose nanofiber (CNF) is attractive as well for its sustainable origin and mechanical properties. However, it can also have excellent adhesion of nanoparticles when it is negatively charged (Lin et al. [46], Li et al. [47], Wang et al. [48], He et al. [49]). In **figure 3Ci**, [45] spontaneous electrostatic self-assembly was used to produce negatively charged CNF-based nanopaper electrodes. Its multilayer architecture (see **figure 3Cii**) provided a good electrolyte retention in compacted film, guaranteeing a quick ion and electron transfer kinetics within the nanopaper electrode. Moreover, because the nanopaper can be densified, the compact density, which is approximately 1.55 g cm³ (see **figure 3Ciii**), is better than in conventional Lithium Iron Phosphate electrodes, which have around 0.8 g cm³ ([45], Wang et al. [50]).

Supercapacitors are of great interest for wearable electronics (Xu et al. [40], Fu et al. [51], Liu et al. [52], Li et al. [53]). Innovative methodologies have been implemented to obtain the trilayer architecture needed for this kind of electronic device. Traditional electrospinning, for example, can produce supercapacitors with up to 50 layers with capacitance values of 3.2 mF cm⁻² (Nagle et al. [54]). Chaotic printing, on the other hand, can produce up to 128 layers with capacitance values of 100 mF cm⁻² approx. (Holmberg et al. [55]). With the incorporation of internal layers in the extruded fibers, the improvement in capacitance is evident. It can be appreciated that the number of layers is closely related to the capacitance values of supercapacitor fibers, taking in account a good distribution of the conductive nanoparticles in the inks used, which in both cases were carbon allotropes.

Methodologies for their obtention have used, as shown, conductive polymers and nanoparticles, but also other conductive materials like MXene. MXene are two dimensional (2D) layered materials with inherently good conductivity. Yang et al. [56] fabricated MXene-based fibers through wet spinning (see **figure 3Di**). The wet-spinning assembling technique was carefully chosen to assemble graphene oxide liquid crystals and the MXene. Making

fibers of MXene material is challenging due to its solid-like and easily oxidized configuration; hence, the post-extrusion coagulation bath helped to produce and collect continuous fibers of the resulting material. Multilayered architecture was obtained; SEM images of the fibers at 10 micrometer and 500 nm resolutions are shown in **figure 3Dii**. The overall fiber electrical conductivity was $2.9 \times 10^4 \text{ S m}^{-1}$, with a superior volumetric capacitance of 586.4 F cm^{-3} . Other innovative extrusion techniques of similar conductive characteristics have been reported, representative viable ways to obtain conducting fibers with supercapacitance properties (Holmberg et al. [57], Babu et al. [58]).

We can conclude that multilayer conductive systems can be produced utilizing nanomaterials, polymers, and MXenes through self-assembling, hydrothermal, additive manufacturing and wet-spinning techniques. Layers intercalation, porosity, and a highly orientated architecture can result in highly-efficient ion transportation channels, causing not only excellent capacitance values, but also excellent mass loading, electrolyte permeability, and flexible low-cost characteristics. Moreover, the architecture design was demonstrated to be relevant when designing new conductive materials with thickness-independence capacitance values.

2.3. Controlled delivery systems

Architectural design is also important in new drug delivery systems, which are vital for treating and preventing diseases in an effective and focalized way. Targeted, controllable, and pH responsive delivery is the aim, hence, multifunctionality is required, and it can be provided by multilayers systems (Volodkin et al. [59], Matsusaki and Akashi [60], Kim et al. [61]). For its development, biological barriers that can obstruct when targeting specific tissues must be understood (Tao and Desai [62], Zhao et al. [63]). In the following discussion, current literature about multilayers systems and their contribution to drug delivery development will be presented.

One of the most researched techniques to produce multilayer architectures for drug delivery systems is Layer-by-layer (LbL) assembly (Linnik et al. [64]). Encapsulations found in nature laid the foundation of LbL technologies (Diamond [65]). Even though cell encapsulation is a crucial application of LbL (Gerelli et al. [66]), in the present work we will focus on the construct and

Figure 4: Multilayers in controlled delivery systems. **A**) Nanoporous films for antigen protein release: **i** Nanoporosity methodology, **ii** Influence of multilayer/porous structure in drug release, **iii** . FE SEM images of 10 micrometers and 30 nm (left to right) [4]. **B**) Antibiotic release coating: **i** Bacterial adhesion for pH response surface, **ii** % of surface coverage vs 0, 12, and 18 number of layers, **iii** Live and death of 6 layers model [68]. **C**) Cell culture environment control through PEMs: **i** Multilayers impact, **ii** Release factor of fibroblast growth factor 2 (FGF2), **iii** Conc. ng/ml vs days [74]. **D**) LbL transcutaneous drug or vaccine delivery: **i** Biodegradable polymer-based LbL multilayered films, **ii** AFM surface topology (2 micrometers), **iii** Normalized curves of the kinetics of ova and CpG release [76].

surface modification provided by different horizontal layers with architectures like the exemplified in **figure 1**.

Normally, LbL assembly relies on the alternate adsorption of oppositely charged molecules through, generally, cost-effective methods. Yang et al. [5], for example, assembled a tetralayered protein delivery system relying on the electrostatic charges of the layers' components. The methodology, shown in **figure 4Ai**, started with assembling 4 layers: branched poly(ethylene imine) (BPEI), negatively charged hyaluronic acid (HA), positively charged gold nanoparticles (Au NPs), and negatively charged HA. Then, they provided porosity to the system by chemically dissolving the AuNPs, obtaining a highly porous BPEI/HA/HA construct. The difference in architecture before and after the removal of AuNPs can be seen in **figure 4Aiii**. Both constructs were later submerged in Ovalbumin (Ova), a widely used globular protein for antigen modeling (Miyazaki [67]). Even though they both were exposed to the same amount of Ova, the BPEI/HA/HA system loaded twice as much Ova because of its porosity. Moreover, the normalized Ova release, shown in **figure 4Aii**, shows a more rapid and controlled release Yang et al. [5]. A multilayer system, hence, was proven to be a promising way to release proteins like Ova in a rapid, cost-effective, and constant manner, highlighting the relevance of the porosity and layers characteristics in LbL generated systems. When drugs of interest are within a multilayered structure, thus, a controlled release is possible due to the multifunctionality of the layers.

Other than to modify internal architectures, Lbl can also be used to modify the surface. Albright et al. [68] developed an LbL hydrogel coating with the ability to adhere bacteria on the surface, like shown in **figure Bi**, with the final objective to have a pH-triggered antibiotic release. The numbers of layers did not seem to affect significantly in the bacteria adhesion (see **figure Bii** and **Biii**), which is interesting because if they were to modify the inner parts of the layers, the bacteria adhesion may not be affected. Coating like the developed can aid as antimicrobial-hosting films in many drug delivery applications, as portrayed by Macha et al. [69] for drug delivery in dental, orthopaedic and neural, or by Pan et al. [70] to prevent implant-related infections. Moreover, it reinforces the statements found in literature that claim that adhering bacteria produce highly localized pH changes even in buffer (Albright et al. [68], Hong and Brown [71], Reddy et al. [72]).

A more sophisticated LbL application are polyelectrolyte multilayers (PEMs). They are materials based on LbL alteration that can not only enable the absorption, modify surface properties, and control growth factor release, but also they can modify topography (Gribova et al. [73]). Ding et al. [74] used PEMs to control the cell fate within cell culture surfaces. In **figure 4Cii**, the release of the fibroblast growth factor was observed to not be proportional to adsorption concentration within the 7 days of the study. This is aligned with literature, concluding that the adsorption of proteins depends not only on charge-charge interactions, but also on the combination of hydrophobic and hydrophilic forces between individual protein molecules and the layers (Lee et al. [7], Yang et al. [5]). Furthermore, studies like de Avila et al. [75]’s reinforce the relevance of the correct alternation of polyelectrolyte layers to deliver antibiotics. Finally, after testing all conditions that helped cells proliferate in low serum media in a 96-well plate (see **figure 4Ciii**), the release rate was observed and, if it is sufficiently high, keeping growth factors within a desired concentration is possible. Topology and water contact angle were of special interest (see **figure 4Ci**), because a correlation between them and the release profiles exists. Surfaces of layers, therefore, play a crucial role, as well as in Su et al. [76]’s work, where macromolecular cargos were released into skin through the usage of PEMs too (see **figure 4Di** and **4Dii**). The results of their study showed an attractive advantage of multilayered systems: multiple components loading.

Su et al. [76] developed a transcutaneous drug and vaccine release multilayered system, where both protein antigen and an adjuvant cargo (used for bettering the vaccine dosage) with unique kinetic properties each. Films of a cationic poly(-amino ester) (denoted Poly-1) with Ova, and/or immunostimulatory CpG (Cytosine-phosphate diester—Guanine rich) DNA oligonucleotide adjuvant molecules were constructed based on electrostatic interactions between each component.. In **figure 4Diii**, architecture “B” (red line) showed a release kinetic attractive for the desired transcutaneous drug and vaccine delivery sought by the authors. This architecture consisted of bilayers of CpG, where Ova was deposited underneath them so that a great amount of component’s quantities could be present in the film. Furthermore, the release study of both components showed how different kinetics applied for them: antigen was released within 24 h, while the CpG adjuvant exhibited sustained release over a period of 3 days (Su et al. [76]). After observing the different interleaving of layers and architectures, Ova was observed repeti-

tively near the surface of every architecture tested, indicating the potential for interdiffusion of the adsorbing species during assembly. This further explains the relevance of surfaces in transcutaneous antigen drug release.

In conclusion, kinetics are crucial for prolonged and immediate deliveries, and they can be induced simultaneously when needed if LbL approaches in PEMs are carried out. In other words, dual release of components is possible due to multilayer architectures. The relevance of the intercalation and modifications of different layers are directly related to the functionality of the controlled drug delivery construct, interfering in the biocompatibility and drug loading and dosage. PEMs, moreover, are obtained through LbL methodologies, allowing pH and temperature-induced deliveries. Architecture matters in controlled delivery systems.

2.4. Sensing

Architecture in sensing devices plays a vital role in their electron transport, mechanical, and weight principally (Cardoso et al. [77], Tripathi et al. [78], Siqueira Jr et al. [79], Xu et al. [80], Espid and Taghipour [81]) The high interest in sensing technologies comes from the highly valuable insights it can give for the better understanding of our health and/or environment Li et al. [82]. Sensing allows us to take the *in vitro* testing to the next level by providing the potential for prolonged non-invasive monitoring of property of interest. Dependence on the layer configurations in the properties of innovative sensing devices will be discussed and are summarized in *table 1*.

Table 1: Summary of multilayered bioinspired sensors in this review.

Bioinspiration	Layers	Sensing	Application	Ref
Gradient gaps	By FDM	Thermal stimuli	Humanoid	[86]
Skin somatosensory	Spin-coating	Soft pressure	Soft robots	[88]
Onion's dermis	By MCQMs	Human respiration	Wearables	[93]
Hoplita coerulea	Spin-coating	Environ. moisture	Materials	[94]

Additive manufacturing is an effective and intuitive way to produce multilayered materials in one or a few steps. However, for sensing purposes combining stimuli-response material is necessary. To achieve this synergy, 4D printing methodologies have been used. **Figure 5 Ai** shows the 4D

Figure 5: Multilayer relevance in sensing technologies. **A)** 4D printed PISA sensor to sense thermal stimuli: **i** Fused deposition modeling (FDM) printing (inks: carbon black (CB) and polylactic acid (PLA)), **ii** Bioinspired gradient microgap structures (500nm) **iii** Touching point was about 14.37 s at frequency of 4 Hz and at displacement of 8 m [86]. **B)** Flexible dual-mode pressure sensor: **i** Bio-inspired skin model, **ii** Pyramidal architecture of the piezoelectric layer (100 micrometers), **iii** Pyramidal, hemisphere, and cylinder piezoelectric stress distribution [88]. **C)** MXene/chitosan-quercetin multilayers (MCQMs) for human respiration detection: **i** Onion-inspired assemble, **ii** Multilayered internal architecture (200 nm), **iii** X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) spectra of newly prepared MCQMs and MCQMs kept in air for 15 days [88]. [93]. **D)** Humidity sensor with color-changing features **i** Silk and titanate nanosheets layers of the sensor **ii** Cross-section SEM image (200nm) of architecture **iii** Transmittance spectra of the multilayer when RH is increased from 10 to 80 % [88]. [94].

printed sensor produced by Chen et al. [83]. Through the usage of nanocarbon black/polylactic acid composites inks and in a fused deposition modeling (FDM) printer, printed integrated sensor–actuators (PISA) were made possible. Its sensing properties were used not only to actively touch objects triggered by thermal stimulation, but also to self-sense the touching state through the resistance change (Chen et al. [83]). These characteristics have a potential use in the incorporation inside humanoid robots’ communication (Dario et al. [84]). Scorpions’ internal physiological gaps used to detect mechanical stimuli of its prey were the bioinspiration for the gradient gaps used to improve the mechanical sensitivity of the PISA, shown in **figure 5 ii**. From the resistance curve in **figure 5Aiii**, the different stages in “touching” process of the PISA is followed, showing resemblance with the touch of a human finger. Their potential incorporation in humanoid robots’ communication is of current interest (Dario et al. [84]).

Many other bio-inspired sensors exist. Qiu, Y et al [85]) created a multilayered pressure sensor inspired by the somatosensory dual mode pressure sensor system of our skin using piezoelectric and piezoresistive layers (see **figure 5 Bi**). Piezoelectric materials are commonly used in sensors due to its inherent transducer characteristics needed in sensing (Vijaya [86]). To increase the piezoelectric and piezoresistive layers within the sensor, pyramidal shapes of these materials were incorporated, as the SEM image (100 micrometers resolution) shows in **figure 5 Bii**. This shape was chosen after comparing with cylindrical and hemispherical configurations (see **figure 5 Biii**).because the large contact area it could create. Soft robotics and health monitoring are some innovative industries in which this kind of highly sensitive to pressure sensors can be applied (Pan et al. [87]. Ashuri et al. [88], Zhu et al. [89]).

Wearable human health physiological monitoring, like previously mentioned, is a growing market that can be benefitted form multilayers architecture. Human respiration is interesting to monitor due to its vital role in human life and illnesses. (Li et al. [90]) developed a sensor to monitor breathing in real time with high resolution through laser induced electrodes in a layer-by-layer methodology. **Figure 5 Ci** shows the bioinspiration of the design: onions’ dermis, because of its good hydrophilicity and water permeance. The sensor multilayer architecture was constructed through MXene/chitosan-quercetin multilayers (MCQMs), which results can be seen

in the cross-sectional SEM image in **figure 5 Cii**. The sensitivity of water molecules was excellent and showed an ultra fast response of 0.75 s. In **figure 5 Ciii**, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) spectra of newly prepared MCQMs is presented. When compared with MCQMs kept in air for 15 days, the difference was negligible, leading to conclude that the surface functional groups of the top layer were maintained. Hence, the multilayer sensor with MCQMs can be a viable way to monitor breathing.

However, humidity sensors can be made with other characteristics as well. There is a beetle species that can change color when in presence of moisture: *Hoplia coerulea*. Colusso et al. [91] were inspired by this beetle to create a humidity sensor with color changing indicator properties. The multilayers, shown in **figure 5 Di**, were made by spin-coating. Because silk fibroin and titanate nanosheets (TNSs) layers were used, the material can be considered a nanocomposite. **Figure 5 Dii** reveals the internal layer interweaving of both materials in a SEM image. The thickness and amount of layers were significant for the sensing properties. A Bragg diffraction peak at approximately 400 nm is needed to sense humidity, and with only 4 layers in the construct, this wavelength was achieved (**figure 5 Diii**). Furthermore, long-term stability and reproducibility were proven, which is important for the future application of this technology.

In conclusion, multilayers in sensor architectures are an attractive opportunity to improve mechanical, electrical, and sensorial properties within light, compact and cost-efficient constructs. The inspiration in nature was made clear by the selected literature examples, showing a representative sample of the widely-used bioinspiration in sensing materials. Human health monitoring, soft robot sensations, and human robots' communication are some attractive and viable applications of the multilayered sensors previously discussed. Further research is needed to scale them to an industrial application due to its emerging status.

2.5. Tissue engineering

The usage of biomaterials to control cell proliferation, elongation and rheology are key factors for tissue engineering. Therefore, the inherent properties of biomaterials used in architectures with living organisms are crucial

for the optimal function of the constructs. Adhesion, morphology, proliferation, migration and differentiation are some of the crucial properties needed in engineered tissues MacDonald et al. [92], Cui et al. [93]. Multilayers are desired in these constructs because natural tissues have naturally multiple layers with different functionalities. To understand the support needed for the mechanical and cell interaction of the engineered tissues, the extracellular matrix (ECM) must be studied (Farjanel et al. [94], Boudreau and Jones [95]). Fabrication methodologies have been developed in the last decade, based on nature’s multilayered architectures that have been proven to increase cell and bio-constructs’ interactions. Furthermore, the biocompatibility of micro and nano-fibrous surfaces have attracted much attention for the synergy they can undergo. In the following section, multilayered tissues will be presented. Their summary is in **table 2**.

Table 2: Summary of multilayered tissue engineered in this review

Tissue	Methodology	Layers	Ref
Cornea	Crosslinked (incubation)	Orthogonal intercalation	[99]
Osteochondral	Stem cells differentiation	single-unit trilayers	[104]
Osteogenic	Layers stacking	50 layers	[105]
Muscle	Chaotic printing	8 internal layers	[109]

Cui et al. [96] created an orthogonal-multilayer tissue-engineered (TE) corneal stroma. The assembly technique to produce the multilayers relied in the mechanical effects given by compressed collagen(CC) or stretched compressed collagen (SCC). CC had a random arrangement of the microfibrils and rabbit corneal stromal cells, while in the SCC they were in an orderly direction, orthogonal to its neighbours. After CC and SCC layers were stacked individually and later staked (see **figure 6 Ai**) and crosslinked with each other through incubation (DMEM, 2 hrs in 37 degrees Celcius), they were later washed with PBS and cultured for 7 days. *In vivo* testing of the corneas were made in white rabbit’s eyes, like in other cornea transplants studies (Brady and Madden [97], Xie et al. [98]). The 6 weeks results of the implemented cornea can be seen in **figure 6 Aii**, and its multilayer configuration is shown in the co-focal microscopy in **figure 6 Aiii**. (Cui et al. [96])’s TE corneal stroma mimicking showed excellent optical and biocompatibility features, proving to be a viable way to engineer this tissues. The optical properties of corneas are challenging to replicate. What multilayers can do, hence, is provide a specific architecture with strategic angles and, through the

Figure 6: Multilayers in tissue engineering. **A)** Cornea tissue: **i** Orthogonal layers intercalation **ii** Cornea tissue implant in rabbits, **iii** Micrograph showing the multilayers loaded with cells (100 micrometers) [99]. **B)** Osteochondrial tissue: **i** Single-unit trilayer scaffold configuration **ii** Multilayer SEM image (50 micrometers). **iii** Live/dead and Hoechst (nucli) assays of each layer (scale bar 200 micrometers) [104]. **C)** Osteogenic tissue: **i** Multilayer obtention methodology **ii** SEM images of the 50 layered architecture (1 mm to 25 micrometers resolutions) **iii** Microscopy after 21 days [105]. **D)** Muscle tissue: **i** Chaotic printing technique using the Kenics Static Mixer, **ii** Chaotic internal layers configuration (live/dead), **iii** Orientation of F-actin throughou 28 days [109].

usage of biomaterials, give a beneficial biocompatibility that were accepted by the rabbit's systems.

Other engineered tissues have been produced through innovative multilayer techniques as well. Engineered osteochondral tissues with different architectures have been studied in this decade, encountering huge relevance of architectures in the interaction between the implant and recipient site (Shao et al. [99], Da et al. [100]). A single-unit trilayer scaffold with depth-varying pore architecture is one of the most innovative ways to produce osteochondral tissues; design and methodology was developed by (Kang et al. [101]). By attaching mesenchymal stem cells in the designed multilayered scaffold, they were able to achieve a differentiation into the osteogenic lineage in a 14-days period. This multilayer scaffold, shown in **figure 6 Bi** is composed of 3 layers. Bottom layer was biomineralized to mimic the calcium phosphate (CaP)-rich bone microenvironment; it was used to support bone formation and it does not have cells. Middle layer has a cryogel with anisotropic pore architecture; it was used to support cartilage tissue formation. Finally, the top layer is composed solely of hydrogel and, as the middle layer, it was loaded with cells prior to implantation. Their *in vitro* architecture can be appreciated in the SEM images of **figure 6 Bii**. Furthermore, they were implemented *in vivo*, resulting in a formation of osteochondral tissue with a lubricin-rich cartilage surface. Each layer was characterized to see their *in vivo* cell behavior (see **figure 6 Biii**), proving that the partially loaded trilayered scaffold is viable as an engineered tissue. The strategic stacking of layers, cell loaded or not, is crucial to replicate bone structures because the natural state of this biomaterial is layered.

Parmaksiz et al. [102] developed osteogenic tissue through multilayers as well. Their assembly methodology was through the stacking of decellularized bovine small intestinal submucosa (bSIS) layers with both synthetic hydroxyapatite microparticles (HAp) and poly(-caprolactone) (PCL) as the binder. The bSIS-PCL/HAp composite, shown in **figure 6 Ci**, had gaps that facilitated the bone structure resemblance. SEM micrographs show regularly spaced layers in the overall construct (see **figure 6 Cii**). These layers facilitated the biocompatibility, which was tested for 21 days using rat bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells (BM-MSCs), as shown in **figure 6 Ciii**. The overall life of the tissue, though, was 14 days, displaying the need for further studies.

Muscle tissues can be produced through multilayer arrangements through different methodologies (goins2019multi, Gao et al. [103], Apsite et al. [104]). The majority of them require multiple steps to acquire the multilayer architecture, making one-steps methodologies attractive. Chaotic methodologies have been used for bioprinting fibers with internal orderly, highly reproducible, and low-cost multilayers (Chávez-Madero et al. [105]). With respect to muscle biofabrication, Bolívar-Monsalve et al. [106] used chaotic bioprinting to obtain resilient C2C12 loaded muscle fibers (81% of the printed fibers lived for 28 days). Even though this technique involves extrusion, the cell viability post-printing was close to 86%, making it attractive. The methodology involves a Kenics Static Mixer, which works as a printhead that provides the fluids' intercalation in a chaotically way; its structure is shown in **figure 6 Di**. When the co-extrusion happens, the 2 inks (both based in pristine alginate, but only one loaded with muscle C2C12 cells) encounter a bath of calcium chloride, causing an ionic gelation that solidifies and encapsulates the fiber constructs. The resulting architecture is shown in **figure 6 Dii** through a live and death cell viability test. The cells arrange themselves in the predicted chaotic pattern, and through close monitoring of their behavior, the elongation of the cells within the alginate-based bioinks was calculated. In **figure 6 Diii**, the F-actin elongation pattern is presented, demonstrating the architecture relevance in the guidance of cells, an important feature in tissue engineering (Homma et al. [107], Zhang et al. [108], Tijore et al. [109]).

In this section, we could clearly see how relevant each layer of the tissue engineered constructs is. Bioinspiration is crucial in tissue engineering, requiring highly compatible layers and innovative ways to achieve good mimicking. Cell elongation, biocompatibility, and construct structure aid were the highlights of incorporating multilayers in tissue engineering designs. Characterizations such as Live/dead and nuclei fluorescence assays, SEM, and optic microscopies are of great use in the tissue analysis. Innovative methodologies were presented, revealing new ways to produce cornea, osteo, and muscle tissues, like crosslinking orthogonal layers through their intercalation and incubation to obtain highly biocompatible corneas, stem cells inclusion in trilayers scaffolds to further differentiate them into osteogenic tissue, and even chaotic printing methodologies to obtain in one step 8 internal layers in muscle fibers. The requirement of *in vivo* testing is vital to see the viability of the implantation and usage of laboratory produced tissue, and it is always required to follow strict ethical and regulatory standards to ensure good practices.

3. Conclusions

Architectures found in nature have inspired science since the beginning of mankind. Materials and biomaterials encounter interesting and useful properties if a bioinspired multilayer is used in their designs. Multilayers have been proven useful in making materials more mechanically robust, more resistant to fracture and with a desired ductility depending on their application. Also, in electrical properties, the assembling of multiple layers can achieve excellent mass loading, electrolyte permeability, and flexible low-cost characteristics, making innovative supercapacitors, electrodes, and conducting materials in general. Moreover, drug delivery systems can take advantage of this kind of architecture as well. Layer-by-layer methodologies empower delivery systems to have multifunctionalities, and even make the dosage of two different treatments with individual kinetics possible in only one multilayer construct. Sensors have used multilayered bioinspiration to produce more sensitive, eco-friendly, flexible, and biocompatible sensors. Finally, multilayers in tissue engineering are crucial for organs's resemblance, biocompatibility, and multifunctionality. Overall, architecture of materials and biomaterials matter. The multilayer bioinspiration have aid in the design of innovative solutions to relevant subjects for today and future matters.

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